

Frontiers of Quantum Gravity and Nature of Space-Time

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Abstract- The research review article discusses about confabulations on theory of quantum gravity, by addressing the existing knowledge on classical physics, and drawing the initiation towards quantum nature of matter. Paper establishes certain strong reasons on the quest towards unified theory. It demonstrates a theoretical aspect on possible building method for theory of everything. Discussions about existing novel ideas in resurrecting the theory. A discourse on popular contemporary ways on quantized theory of gravitational force. Paper inspects the features and characteristics of space-time, as interrelated. Explores reasons on existing knowledge and possible relations amongst fundamental theories.

Index Terms- Quantum Gravity, Relativity, Space-Time, Quantum Field Theory, Quantization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The early twentieth century has witnessed the development of a principal idea, that matter at its core is quantum in nature, that laid to the foundation of quantum mechanics. Erwin Schrodinger has introduced the pivotal Schrodinger's cat experiment to demonstrate the dual nature of matter, alongside the works of Max Planck's statement that Energy is quantizable. The wing of this physics has attracted brilliant minds, in its progress and developments.

The universe, as we experience, encapsulates variety of phenomenon. The stars that go around the galaxies, the planets that orbits the stars, humans that stand still on the surface. The reason behind all of this entire phenomenon is Gravity. First ever description on gravitational force is given by Sir Isaac Newton in year 1687 through his published work. It gave a very vivid description on the magnitude and strength of force acting on the other. Newton described this as "*Gravity is a mysterious force that acts on very massive objects that are separated at any distance.*" Newton's elucidation on Gravity has provided a concise view on the first discovered fundamental force. Later, as time progressed, this stance has faced certain challenges.

The following theory of gravity is provided by Albert Einstein in early 1900's – that went by the name '*General Theory of Relativity*'. Explanation by Einstein was much more enhanced and pictured a clear thought on Gravity.

We have acknowledged earlier about the elemental nature of matter – quantum, not classical. Yet general relativity is classical. If we meaningfully try to merge Einstein's theory into a quantum

model of gravity, it provides absurd results.

Due to these unclear results, there have been questions whether the framework of quantum nature is true or not. Scientists have started to observe the other side of the coin, instead of pushing the gravity into display of quantum, *why not to perform the opposite?* Encompassing other three fundamental forces into classical view or into general relativity.

Why must we quantize gravity? This has been the central idea of this research paper, that allows us to explore various possibilities.

Reason 1 - All of the fundamental forces that are in our knowledge are quantized – except Gravity. The evolution and improvement of three quantized theories has led to a thought that, even Gravity can be done in the same manner. If not, why would universe make an exception for gravity? Is it supposed to be treated in a unique manner, or isn't it? *Gluon, Photon, Weak and Z Boson* – all of these force carriers have been completely transformed and exists in quantum description of matter. Mathematics does work for set one equation for three of these forces, and not for gravity. It led to some bizarre conclusions.

Reason 2- Our accurate representation of gravity is provided by general theory of relativity. As far this is concerned, this is entirely from a lens of classical point of view. This theory fails at close to the time of universe's creation – (at the big bang) – it does not provide a comprehensive understanding in that state of universe. General theory does not provide us anything at beginning, when most of the matter existed in quantum nature.

Another location – at the center of black hole. The postulates of relativity fails and breakdowns at this point. Theoretically, it is a point with mass but almost no volume – which represents an infinite dense object. Mathematically, this region is known to be a singularity.

A singularity in math is equivalent to pushing the equations of general relativity beyond its limits and getting incoherent conclusions. Thus, a quantum level of acknowledgement is needed to overcome this back draw.

II. RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

Inspecting Equation of Relativity –

When we look a bit closely towards the *equation*, we get on the left-hand side, two components. The curvature of space-time in different permutations. The negative component represents stress due to free space. (Figure 1)

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$$

Fig 1. Field Equations of General Relativity

Combination of these two aspects is merely telling the curvature which is continuous and classical. It solidifies the continuous bent or distortion in the fabric of space-time.

Opposite part of the equation represents matter and its configurations – at core which is quantum as we have established. With a constant (known to be Einstein’s constant), it establishes the equality factor. Through viewing from out, this equation consists two incompatible possibilities – both continuous nature of space-time and quantum nature of matter.

Thus, we reach a point in our discussion that – if we try to create a theory of gravity compatible with matter – then it must obey the quantum nature of matter. How would a rough idea of *Quantum Theory of Gravity* look like? Let’s go through a conceptual approach.

3D Bronstein Cube

Now we build up a model that provides an assumed structure of quantum gravity, by putting each component on one over the other. Imagine the fundamental theories in three different directions – (namely x, y and z), keeping the signature constants in each axis direction. Special theory of relativity is along the y direction, portrayed by speed of light constant (1/c). Along the x – direction, we have the way for Quantum Mechanics which carries the Planck’s Constant (h). In the top direction z, we have the Newtonian Gravity, which says Universal Gravitation constant (G). (Figure 2)

At the origin of the cube, classical mechanics resides, where particles, matter and forces exist without the effect or influence of relativistic effects, gravity or quantum fluctuations. Moving along the (G) - axis, introduces concept of gravity and interactions of matter as a result of gravitational force. Along (1/c) axis – it opens the behaviour of matter as a constraint of speed of light (c). Towards the other (h) axis, the quantum world opens and all matter and interactions would be governed by Planck’s constant.

When we turn each respective axis, we turn on each theory along with the constant. With these three core constraints, we can classify the theories into the representation of 3-Dimensional Bronstein Cube.

When we turn on both special relativity and Newtonian gravity at same time, we reach the corner of general relativity, in the region of y-z plane. When we turn on both special relativity and quantum mechanics, then we open *Quantum Field Theory* (QFT). QFT is the most precise one, that describes the standard model of particle physics, which encompasses both matter and force carrying particles.

The search for quantum gravity can be found when we turn all *ON* these axes at same time, which is turning the Speed of light, Newtonian Gravity along with Planck’s constant.

There are two methods. Obtaining quantum field theory in association with Newtonian gravity – or – establishing

Fig 2. - 3-Dimensional Representation of Bronstein cube

Planck’s constant with general relativity. Either of these two integrations would create a rough *quantum theory of gravity*. Theoretical goal of this initiative is to incorporate quantum mechanics along with Newtonian gravity, that allows to unify the gravitational as well as the quantum effects, known also as theory of everything. Yet, this 3D Bronstein cube encompasses dimension full entities, it refers to physical quantities that aren’t directly measurable and acknowledged.

Reasons for Quantization failure -

Why have we failed to quantize gravity in the first place? What went wrong in its process? Let’s discuss how the other forces have been converted very accurately without any sort of hiccups. All the forces of our universe, have been following one same method for quantization. Take a classical theory and quantize it by discrete forms, this would yield some fundamental mathematics. This procedure essentially involves considering certain physical quantities in the theory and turning them into operators by means of incorporating a hat in notations. (Figure 3)

This standard method of conversion has worked for distinct cases. For electromagnetism, the field equations of electric and magnetic fields are quantized. Physically, this indicates that the classical structures of these physical quantities are transformed into quantum objects, and math turns compatible for this level. As far Electromagnetism is concerned, quantization occurs for Maxwell’s set of equations, known by a procedure called QED (Quantum Electrodynamics). When we apply this procedure in case of gravity, by incorporating for equations of general relativity, it provides all possible cancellations and then infinity. Now, we shall understand the other views in this discussion.

III. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Medium Perspective –

Unique factor of general relativity is, it’s a theory of a medium, a theory of space-time itself. It’s not saying about the force nor does not describe about the matter, situated within the space-time.

When we address about space-time, we refer to nothing being in the place. Then gravity is a resultant due to massive objects bending the free space and causing curvature, thus creating a line of force from one end to the other following the established trajectory.

$$\mathbf{p} = m\mathbf{v} \quad \hat{\mathbf{p}} = -i\hbar\nabla$$

$$\hat{p} = -i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial x}$$

Fig 3. Linear momentum and hat incorporated operator momentum equations

In contrast, other three forces describe a theory that says about the matter and its interactions due to the respective force. Other classical theories have been quantized, it justifies that their quantum approach constitutes the force that it mentions. But gravity is something that is a result of presence of matter in the fabric of free space-time, thus quantization here theoretically doesn't reach the gravity. Thus, what should be looking for, is a potential *quantum theory of space-time*. This can be synonymous to quantum gravity.

Challenging factors to Quantize -

1. *Incompatible Math* - General relativity uses tensors and continuous forms of expressions, on the opposite hand, quantum mechanics uses discrete functions (locations and speeds) to represent them.
2. *Weak Nature* - Quantization has become a challenge, for another reason that gravitational force is so weak when compared to electromagnetism. The strength of electromagnetism is 10 on order of 40, greater than the actual gravitational force. This is the reason a small magnet can uplift a nail against the gravitational force of the entire earth. With these observations, we may say that creating a quantum theory of gravity can be completely thought experiment – that assumes specific limitations and features.

Fields Procedure -

We should not come to a conclusion that quantizing gravity is impossible. There are some ways to do so, which are beyond the general thoughts. *The procedure of quantizing through fields is another promising method.* (Figure 4)

Fig 4. Fields of gravitational force and graviton particle

Considering gravity as a field, analogous to electromagnetic field, an excitation in the gravitational field is a hypothetical *graviton* particle. As exchange of photon (force carrying particle) leads to electromagnetic attraction or repulsion, an exchange of gravitons would result in gravitational force between two

massive objects. This would be from a force field perspective, which could lead to inclusion of a new particle, if discovered, into the standard model of particle physics. We have two major theories, supporting this way.

Two Approaches of Quantum Gravity –

Method 1 -

String Theory says, smallest and most fundamental building blocks of universe are not made of particles or matter, but due to vibrations of a single one-dimensional string material.

Fig 5. Depiction of sub-atomic particles in the form of fundamental strings

Consider a matter particle and let's dissect it to depths, as you go deeper, you find a molecule and then atoms. Inside the atom, when we go through, most volume exists as an empty space, but we find a tiny centered nucleus. Inside this nucleus we have two types of particles the neutrons and the protons, if I consider a proton and magnify it to the maximum, we find still small particles which form the standard model of particle physics, *quarks*. This is end of the conventional idea, yet inside the quarks we have the hypothetical strings which are a simple one-dimensional matter that resemble these sub atomic particles as a result its own vibrations.

These strings exist in both open and closed loops, that oscillate in various frequencies and in ten different dimensions. Entire colossal of standard particles are an outcome of this string, that vibrates at different frequencies. (Figure 5)

According to theory, known sub atomic particles are not different objects, but different vibrations of same fundamental string. One such one vibration that oscillates in those 10 dimensions, is indistinguishable from a graviton – the hypothetical force carrying gravity particle.

Method 2-

Loop Quantum Gravity – the approach deals with space-time itself, and not with any matter or particles, reflecting on the possibility for discovering a quantum theory of medium. As we have initially addressed that gravity is an outcome of curvature, so this method deploys the description within the space-time. The theory says that entire space-time is formed due to finite stitched loops that are woven as fabric. It says that space and time are quantized in this manner, constituting a basic unit as its quanta. These tiniest loops stitched one next to the other in all three dimensions form an enormous fabric of space-time reality.

The smallest possible time and length, are Planck time = 10^{-43} seconds and Planck length = 10^{-35} meters. This unit potentially acts as quantum object of space-time.

$$v = c \cdot \left(1 - \xi \cdot \frac{\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{L}{1 + \frac{a^2}{2r^2} \cdot \cos^2(\theta)} \right)$$

Fig 6. Equation of velocities of light for various wavelengths. – Loop Quantum Gravity

The math of loop quantum gravity says that light of different wavelengths depicts variety of speeds, theoretically. (Figure 6) An electromagnetic wave (or light) of higher energy and shorter wavelength would travel *slower* than a light of longer wavelength. The difference of this propagation would be very slight and imperative. For specifications, omega – frequency, theta – rotation parameter and xi – polarization state.

An experiment was conducted to examine this, where electromagnetic waves those emitted from a very powerful gamma ray bursts, had been observed to detect these slightest different velocities. An expectation would be that these waves would reach the Earth at distinct times. But nothing deviation was found till date.

IV. CONCLUSION

The entire view on the theory of quantum gravity can only be unified, when the theory of general relativity respects and understand the quantum nature of matter and energy. A unified theory is only possible when all the constraints and restrictions are gently removed or crossed with other specified conditions.

Alongside, this discussion could be a simple piece towards the attainment of the right theory, or even may be a completely wrong model. Thus, quantum description of the gravitational force is always in search all the time.

The rest of the three forces electromagnetism, strong and weak nuclear forces have got quantized way long ago. Result of the unification of the quantization of gravity would lead to the ultimate theory and unlock many other new existing problems.

The dark matter and dark energy, situation of the universe at the Big Bang (the Lambda CDM model) and the quantum nature of matter and Quantum fluctuations at the black hole. These are the potential candidates that can be understood in an enhancement mode through the ultimate triumph of quantum gravity.

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